

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	1
Work Package title	Project management and coordination of activities
Deliverable number	1.4.5
Deliverable title	Financial report #5
Deliverable Responsible Partner	CMCC
Deliverable Lead authors	Paola Agostini (CMCC)
Deliverable Contributors	Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)
Deliverable due date	2021-12-31
Deliverable latest review date	2022-03-22

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Project progress.....	2
2.1 General achievements	2
2.2 Unforeseen issues.....	5
2.2.1 CMCC.....	5
2.2.2 CSA	5
2.2.3 UniZd	5
2.2.4 MMPI.....	5
2.2.5 AdSP	5
3. Conclusions	6

1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project financial progress during the reporting period ranging from 2021-07-01 to 2021-12-31, corresponding to RP6. Full reporting information is declared on SIU and the present report just represents an overview of its key contents. Moreover, the report does not consider possible modifications to the present conditions, which may rise during the work of the FLCs. When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which is found at:

<https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect. 2.1), and Unforeseen Issues (Sect. 2.2).

2.1 General achievements

For the first time, expenditures for RP6 were reported in SIU by all PPs of GUTTA. Due to the COVID-19, travelling was still absent, and expenditures of partners were mainly related to staff costs. External costs included FLCs expenses and a subcontract by MMPI.

Expenditures were generally occurring in a regular manner during RP6. Exception remains the situation of PP5-AdSP, which did report only limited costs in this reporting period, and whose projected absorption till project end remain below expectations.

Small adjustments of PP2-CSA budget are reported in the RP6 documentation for minor changes.

The overall financial progress, both at WP, activities, and budget-line levels, is summarized in Fig.1-3.

Figure 1: Financial implementation status of GUTTA WPs. Blue is the absorbed fraction of the budget, cumulative of the first three RPs; orange is the cumulative missing fraction within the current RP, and grey is the remaining fraction until the end of the project.

The WP-breakdown (Fig.1) highlights a complete absorption in both WP3 and WP4. Gaps with respect to planned (underspending) remain mainly in WP5 (Technical), WP2 (Communication) and WP1 (Management). The overall implementation rate, defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption, is 71.8%.

Figure 2: Financial implementation status of GUTTA activities for WPs 1 to 4. Color codes as in Fig.1

Figure 2 reports the cost breakdown at the level of project activities in the different WPs. The technical work of WP3 and WP4 was concluded and related budget spent, except for PP4 and PP5, which probably will leave this amounts unspent up to the end of the project. WP5 started in this reporting period and much should be reported in the next one. WP1 is proceeding quite regularly and WP2 has left some budget from travels and external expertise costs but most of it is going to be recovered in the next reporting period with the two final events in Croatia and Italy and with the communication material production.

The breakdown of the financial absorption into budget lines (Fig.3) shows underspending in this reporting period especially in the lines of external expertise and in travel & accommodation. While the latter is justified by the cancellation of physical meetings due to the ongoing pandemic, the underspending for external expertise has been caused by different postponements and delays, namely: the costs of the video production by LP has been postponed to RP7 and external expertise costs by PP5 were not still reported.

Figure 3: Breakdown of financial implementation status of GUTTA through budget lines. Color codes as in Fig.1

2.2 Unforeseen issues

2.2.1 CMCC

- No issues, except the postponement of the video production and its cost to RP7

2.2.2 CSA

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in this RP documentation.

2.2.3 UniZd

- No issues

2.2.4 MMPI

- No issues.

2.2.5 AdSP

- Limited costs only were claimed in RP6, and projected absorption till project's end is below the threshold of 50,000 EUR (ERDF contribution).

3. Conclusions

As in previous reporting periods, the financial absorption of GUTTA project in RP6 was lower than expected mainly due severe underspending by PP5 and still some impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on some cost categories.

Therefore, pending issues for upcoming RP7 include the absorption of as much as possible of the planned budget and the correct evaluation of project savings up to the end of the project, in order to give back the unspent amounts to the Interreg Programme.